

AN EXPLORATION OF MEITEI THUM: ITS CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE, PRODUCTION, AND CONTEMPORARY RELEVANCE

A CASE STUDY ON MEITEI THUM

*A Dissertation submitted to the Department of History, Manipur University in partial
fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the Master of Arts in History*

Submitted by

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Year 2024

Under the guidance of

DR. BEDAVATI LAISHRAM

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DEPARTMENT OF HISTORY

**DEPARTMENT OF HISTORY
MANIPUR UNIVERSITY
CANCHIPUR, IMPHAL - 795003
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BONA FIDE CERTIFICATE

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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis entitled “**An Exploration of Meitei Thum: Its Cultural Significance, Production, and Contemporary Relevance**” submitted in partial fulfilment of the degree of Master in History is a record of original work carried out by me under the supervision of **Dr. Bedavati Laishram**, and has not formed the basis for the award of any other degree or diploma, in this or any other Institution or University. In keeping with the ethical practice in reporting scientific information, due acknowledgements have been made wherever the findings of others have been cited.

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ABSTRACT

Meitei Thum, a traditional salt from Manipur, India, embodies the rich cultural and historical legacy of the Meitei people. Its production, deeply intertwined with the region's unique geographical features, reflects age-old practices and sustainability. The salt is harvested from natural springs and wells in districts such as Thoubal, Imphal, and Ukhrul, where the distinct geological formations contribute to its unique mineral composition. This traditional method of salt production has been passed down through generations, highlighting the Meitei people's profound connection to their environment and cultural heritage.

Historically, Meitei Thum has been more than a culinary staple; it played a significant role in traditional medicine and various ceremonial practices. The meticulous process of extracting brine, boiling it to evaporate the water, and crystallizing the salt is labor-intensive, requiring considerable skill and patience. This method not only preserves the salt's distinctive qualities but also aligns with sustainable practices, minimizing environmental impact. The salt's production is often accompanied by cultural rituals, emphasizing its spiritual significance and the community's respect for natural resources.

In recent years, there has been a resurgence of interest in traditional and organic food products, including Meitei Thum. This renewed appreciation is driven by a growing awareness of the benefits of traditional food practices and a desire to preserve cultural heritage. Efforts to sustain and promote traditional salt production methods are crucial for maintaining the region's ecological balance and cultural diversity. Local and regional markets increasingly value Meitei Thum for its unique taste, health benefits, and its role as a symbol of cultural identity.

The contemporary relevance of Meitei Thum highlights the importance of integrating traditional practices into modern contexts. By promoting and preserving the traditional methods of Meitei Thum production, the legacy of this cultural treasure can continue to enrich the cultural and ecological landscape of Manipur. This not only supports the local economy but also ensures that future generations can experience and appreciate the cultural significance of Meitei Thum.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Meitei Thum is more than simply salt; it is a representation of the Meitei people of Manipur's rich cultural and historical legacy. Its distinctive qualities, use in cultural rituals, and age-old manufacturing techniques make it an invaluable and treasured component of Manipuri culture. Maintaining the region's natural sustainability and cultural variety depends on keeping this practice alive.

1.1 Background and Context

Geographical and Cultural Context: Meitei Thum is a traditional salt that holds a deep connection to the Meitei people, who are the predominant ethnic group in the northeastern Indian state of Manipur. The production of Meitei Thum is intricately tied to the geographical features and cultural practices of the region. Historically, the Meitei people have utilized the natural salt springs and wells scattered throughout Manipur, particularly in areas such as the Thoubal, Imphal, and Ukhrul districts. These regions are characterized by their unique geological formations, which contribute to the distinct qualities of the salt produced.

Fig 1.1: Meitei Thum (Salt)

The Geological Survey of India (GSI) took an interest in the salt springs of Manipur in the 1960s and 1980s, conducting scientific research to understand the properties of the brines found in various locations including Waikhong, Shikhong, Chandrakhong,

Phonjoukhong, Nongnaukunon, Ningel, Keithelmanbi, Chingai, Mariamphung, Namrei, Chalou, Lachaikhulen, Kharasom, Thiwa, and Sanakeithel village. These studies have highlighted the unique mineral composition of the salt and its significance in the region's ecological and cultural fabric.

Manipur is home to four main brine wells: Waikhong, Chandrakhong, Ningel, and Sikhong. These wells are located in the Thoubal district, with the exception of Waikhong. The distribution and number of these wells were documented in the early 20th century by Allen (1905: 93–94), who noted that Chandrakhong had two wells, Sikhong had four, Ningel had three, and Waikhong had five. Among these, Ningel stands out as the only village that continues to uphold the traditional salt-making customs to this day.

Ningel's salt production is unique, with three wells used for extracting brine. Two of these wells are constructed from concrete, while the third is a remarkable wooden structure. This wooden well is particularly notable for its use of a hollowed-out tree trunk, measuring an impressive 54.5 feet in length, which holds the salt water. Historical accounts credit King Rajshree Bhagyachandra with the construction of this wooden well in the 18th century. This suggests that Ningel's salt-making tradition has deep historical roots and has been a significant part of the region's culture for centuries.

The salt produced in Ningel was highly regarded and widely used throughout the kingdom, indicating its importance and high quality. In contrast, the salt from Chandrakhong was sufficient to meet the needs of the local population, suggesting a more localized production and consumption pattern.

Historical records, such as those by Hudson (1997) in his book "The Meetei," provide further insights into the social and economic aspects of salt production in Manipur. According to Hudson, the Loi communities were specifically assigned to work in salt production. This assignment of labor reflects the structured societal roles and the economic strategies employed by the kingdom to ensure a steady supply of this essential commodity.

The involvement of the Loi communities in salt production underscores the intricate social fabric of Manipur and highlights the communal efforts that sustained the traditional salt-making practices. The continuation of these customs in Ningel today

serves as a living link to the past, preserving an age-old craft that has been integral to the region's history and culture.

Not only salt produced in the valley regions of Manipur, but it is also crafted in the hilly areas, such as Chalou village. Chalou is situated near the Myanmar borders in the Ukhrul District of Manipur and is renowned for its indigenous salt, which is made from a particular spring water found in the village. This unique salt-making tradition is deeply embedded in the culture of the Tangkhul-Naga tribes, who inhabit the region.

The Tangkhul-Naga tribes have a rich repository of folktales and folk songs that revolve around the salt of Chalou. These stories and songs highlight the cultural significance and revered status of Chalou salt within the community. Historically, the people of Chalou engaged in barter trade, exchanging their precious salt with the Meitei people of the valley. This exchange underscores the historical interdependence and trade relationships between the hill and valley communities of Manipur.

Some elders from the region claim that the name "Tangkhul-Atangba Khun," which translates to "precious land," was given by the Meitei people of the valley in recognition of the value of Chalou salt. This name reflects the high esteem in which the salt was held and its importance to the valley communities. The salt from Chalou is believed to possess great medicinal value, making it an essential ingredient in various traditional practices.

Fig 1.2: The Ningel Thumkhong from where saline water was collected.

Fig 1.3 Chandrakhong Thumkhong

Fig 1.4: Waikhong Thumkhong Lairembi

Historical Significance: Salt has been a highly prized commodity in Manipur for millennia, with records of its manufacture and trade dating back to ancient times. The traditional production of Meitei Thum is more than just a method of obtaining salt; it represents a profound historical continuity and a testament to the resourcefulness of the Meitei people. In the past, Meitei Thum was not only a vital component of daily sustenance but also played a crucial role in traditional medicine and various ceremonial practices. The production techniques have been passed down through generations, reflecting the deep connection between the Meitei people and their environment. This generational transmission of knowledge underscores the cultural importance of Meitei Thum, as it symbolizes a lasting bond with the land and its natural resources.

Production Methods: The process of making Meitei Thum involves extracting brine from natural salt springs and wells. The brine is then boiled to evaporate the water,

leaving behind crystallized salt. This traditional method is labor-intensive, requiring considerable skill and patience. The resulting salt is noted for its distinctive mineral composition, which is believed to offer various health benefits compared to commercially processed salts. The traditional method of production also aligns with sustainable practices, minimizing environmental impact and preserving the natural integrity of the region's salt springs.

Cultural Importance: Beyond its practical uses, Meitei Thum holds profound cultural significance. It is often employed in religious rituals and cultural ceremonies, symbolizing purity, prosperity, and the sanctity of life. In Meitei culture, salt is seen as a vital element that connects the physical and spiritual realms. The practices associated with its production and use are integral to the intangible cultural heritage of the Meitei people. These practices are not only a reflection of the community's historical continuity but also serve as a medium through which cultural values and traditions are expressed and maintained.

Contemporary Relevance: In recent years, traditional salt production methods, including those used to produce Meitei Thum, have been facing challenges and are slowly becoming distinct. Despite a global resurgence of interest in traditional and organic food products, Meitei Thum is struggling to maintain its place. This decline is due to various factors such as modernization, the availability of cheaper industrially produced salts, and a lack of awareness about the traditional methods among the younger generations. Efforts to preserve and promote Meitei Thum are crucial not only for its unique taste and potential health benefits but also for its cultural and ecological significance. There is a need for increased awareness and support to integrate these traditional practices into modern contexts, ensuring that the legacy of Meitei Thum does not fade away and continues to be a part of Manipur's rich cultural heritage.

1.2 Research Objective

The primary research objective is to investigate the traditional production methods of Meitei Thum, a culturally significant salt from Manipur, India. This involves an in-depth examination of the historical context, geographical origins, and the evolution of its production over time. The study aims to uncover the intricate connection between the Meitei people and their environment, highlighting how the production of Meitei Thum has been shaped by and, in turn, has shaped the cultural practices and

ecological landscape of the region. By documenting these traditional methods, the research intends to preserve a vital aspect of Meitei heritage that has been passed down through generations.

Furthermore, the study seeks to explore the contemporary relevance of Meitei Thum, particularly in the context of sustainable practices and cultural preservation. As the world increasingly turns towards eco-friendly and sustainable production methods, understanding how traditional techniques can be integrated into modern practices is essential. The research will examine how the time-honored methods of producing Meitei Thum can be adapted to meet contemporary environmental standards without compromising the cultural authenticity and quality of the salt. This involves an analysis of potential improvements in efficiency and sustainability while retaining the traditional essence that defines Meitei Thum.

In addition to the ecological and cultural dimensions, the study aims to identify potential markets for Meitei Thum, both locally and internationally. By exploring the economic viability of this unique salt, the research seeks to ensure its continued production and preservation. This involves market analysis to understand consumer interest, potential applications in various culinary and non-culinary contexts, and the development of branding strategies that emphasize the cultural heritage and ecological benefits of Meitei Thum. Through these efforts, the study hopes to create a sustainable economic model that supports the local communities involved in its production, ensuring that the cultural legacy of Meitei Thum is maintained for future generations.

Ultimately, this research aspires to bridge the gap between traditional knowledge and modern sustainability practices, fostering a greater appreciation for the cultural and ecological significance of Meitei Thum. By bringing this unique salt to a wider audience, the study aims to contribute to the broader discourse on cultural preservation, sustainable development, and the promotion of indigenous knowledge systems.

1.3 Methodology

The methodology for this research involves a multi-faceted approach combining both qualitative and quantitative methods to comprehensively understand the production, cultural significance, and contemporary relevance of Meitei Thum. The first step is conducting extensive fieldwork in the regions of Manipur where Meitei Thum is

traditionally produced. This includes visiting natural salt springs and wells, and observing the production process firsthand. Detailed notes, photographs, and videos are taken to document the traditional methods of brine extraction, boiling, and crystallization of the salt. Interviews with local producers, elders, and community members are conducted to gather insights into the historical and cultural context of Meitei Thum production.

In addition to fieldwork, archival research is conducted to review historical documents, previous studies, and literature related to Meitei Thum. This helps to establish a historical timeline and understand the evolution of salt production methods in Manipur. The collected data is analyzed to identify patterns, common practices, and unique aspects of Meitei Thum production. This historical perspective is crucial for appreciating the cultural heritage and sustainability of traditional salt production practices.

To ensure a comprehensive analysis, the study also incorporates laboratory analysis of Meitei Thum samples. The mineral content and purity of the salt are examined to verify claims about its unique qualities and health benefits. This scientific validation supports the traditional knowledge and practices associated with Meitei Thum production. Additionally, market analysis is performed to explore the economic potential of Meitei Thum. Surveys and interviews with consumers, retailers, and experts in the food industry provide insights into the current demand, potential markets, and economic impact of Meitei Thum.

CHAPTER 2

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF MEITEI THUM

The origins, geographical context, and traditional practices associated with Meitei Thum provide a comprehensive understanding of its historical and cultural significance. From its ancient roots to its role in contemporary society, Meitei Thum represents a rich tradition that has evolved over time. The traditional methods of production, including brine collection, boiling, and storage, reflect the skill and knowledge of Meitei artisans. Efforts to preserve and promote Meitei Thum are essential for maintaining its cultural heritage and supporting sustainable practices in the region.

2.1 Origins of Meitei Thum

Historical Significance

The origins of Meitei Thum trace back to ancient times when salt was a fundamental commodity for the Meitei people. Historical texts, oral traditions, and archaeological evidence highlight the central role of salt in early Meitei society. Salt was not only vital for food preservation and seasoning but also played a crucial role in trade and economy. In historical records, salt production is often mentioned alongside other economic activities, indicating its importance in shaping regional trade routes and economic structures.

In Meitei tradition, certain sacred places and deities are deeply revered, especially those connected with essential resources like salt. Among these, Thum Khong holds particular significance as a holy site. It is believed to be imbued with spiritual importance, where people engage in worship and seek blessings. The deity Thumkhong Lairembi is closely associated with this place and is considered the guardian of salt well.

In Meitei culture, salt has historically been a vital commodity, and thus, the reverence for Thumkhong Lairembi reflects the significance of this resource. This deity is seen as a protector and preserver of salt well, highlighting its importance in daily life and spiritual practices. The origin of salt springs, as narrated in the old manuscript Thumkhonglon, closely parallels the creation myth of the Meiteis. In this myth, the supreme deity Guru Sidaba and his consort Leimarel are central to the creation of the

universe. Guru Sidaba is considered the creator of the universe, while Leimarel is the mother of the universe. Together, they shaped the cosmos, with Leimarel's eyes becoming the Sun and the Moon, her body hairs transforming into the stars and the Khongjomnubi, which is the seven sisters' constellation.

To complete the creation of the earth, Guru Sidaba and Leimarel worked with their three sons—Ngangoi, Yoimongba, and Taothingmang. To sustain life, Leimarel directed her three sons to awaken the six goddesses of prosperity, who were close friends. These goddesses were Noinu Thumleima, Loimom Phouoibee, Lemlei Ngareima, Nganu Leima, Kairei Yenleima, and Charei Phileima.

Thumleima, the goddess associated with salt, first appeared and became known as Thum Ching. She wandered under the soil through the foothills and forests, moving in a northward direction. The three brothers, along with the help of the people, searched for Thumleima by digging trenches. They eventually found her, and this is how the springs were found. Thumleima taught the people how to extract salt from the saltwater. With this newfound knowledge, the people began to produce their own salt, thus discovering the salt springs.

Other sacred sites like Sikhong, Laikhong, and Waikhong are also integral to Meitei spirituality. These places are not only venues for worship but also hold historical and cultural significance. They contribute to the rich tapestry of Meitei religious life, where each location and deity plays a role in maintaining the community's spiritual and cultural heritage.

In the state of Manipur, there are an estimated 450 saline springs, each with unique mineral compositions and varying degrees of salinity. Despite this abundance, a detailed analysis found in the book “Puwari gi Wareng”, compiled by Naoreoibam Indramani and Dr. Haorongbam Rajmani, reveals that only 63 of these springs are considered suitable for human use. This determination is based on several critical factors including the springs' chemical makeup, purity, and the overall suitability of their water for consumption and other uses. These brine wells were divided into two groups Numitloi and Tharoi. Salt well of Ningel and waikhong belonged to the Numitloi groups and Sikhong, Chandrakhong, Chalou, Torbung and Chilbu

belonged to the Tharoi group. The Numitloi salt well fetched one “Thumbon” everyday whereas the Tharoi salt wells fetched 20 thumbons a month.

During the reign of King Kyamba (1467-1508 A.D.), there was a notable influx of immigrants, including war captives who were incorporated into various Meitei clans. Among these immigrants were the Mayang Kalishas, who were skilled in the art of salt production. These immigrants arrived from the western regions, initially settling along the banks of the Leimatak River. The Khuman king Adon Thinkolhanba, who ruled around 930 A.D., conducted raids on their villages to collect salt and later relocated some of these immigrants to Meeyang Yumpham. The Mayang Kalishas continued their traditional practice of salt-making in their new settlements and were later moved to Waikhong, a region renowned for its extensive salt production activities.

The production of salt under the patron of the King was started during the reign of Paikhomba (1666-97). The term salt well was mentioned for the first time in Cheitharol Kumbaba during his reign. In 1693 there is a record of King Paikhomba improving salts well. Waikhong was considered to be one of the prime locations where salts were manufactured mainly for the Royal family. All the wells are considered the properties of the King who levies a tax of 1/5 upon the quantity of water drawn

In the past, the production of salt was managed by an official known as the Thumjaorel. Overseeing the manufacturing and distribution of salt was the responsibility of a royal officer called the Thumjaorongba. This officer was among those who managed the affairs of the Maharaja. Various royal officers were assigned to different tasks: Arangba handled stewardship, Phourungba collected taxes, Thangsa-Pannaba worked as an ironsmith or sword forger, Paija Suba managed carpentry, Hiru-Hinaoba dealt with matters related to boats, Tangkhai Urungba served as an assistant carpenter, Tangkhai Thumjaorongba assisted the salt officer, and Haoba Naha Puren oversaw tribal affairs.

In one notable case, the Thumjaorongba took responsibility for four Panas (Divisions). The individuals responsible for the well-being of the Maharaja were

referred to as Ningthou Senba. Different groups of people were assigned specific roles. Given the importance of salt, the Thumjaorongba oversaw its production and the workers involved in this process. Salt was procured and delivered to the palace on a monthly basis. It was also provided to lactating mothers. A-panois (higher-order queens) received 60 units of salt, while tu ayamba (lesser queens) were given 50 units of salt.

The Pemberton Report of 1835 provides a detailed account of Manipur's salt industry. It highlights the valley's wealth of salt resources, noting significant salt springs at Waikhong, Ningel, Sengmiee, and ChadraKhong. Among these, Waikhong was particularly prized for producing superior salt, which was reserved for the royal family. The process of salt extraction involved detecting salt springs by observing vapor emissions, drilling wells, and using wooden cylinders to collect the brine. The Rajah of Manipur imposed a tax on the extracted salt, and the salt makers were compensated with a portion of the salt. This method of production yielded about 1/19th of the weight of the water used, demonstrating a high level of efficiency compared to other contemporary methods.

Historically, the Loi communities played a crucial role in the salt production industry. They were responsible for various trades and services, including salt manufacturing, for the kings of Manipur. The Loi were engaged in activities such as silk production, iron smelting, spirit distillation, and the creation of earthen vessels. Over time, the term "Loi" evolved, reflecting shifts in social and cultural contexts. Today, "Loi" primarily refers to Scheduled Castes, whereas historically it encompassed a broader range of individuals involved in specific economic roles within the society.

This evolution of the Loi's role and the historical significance of salt production in Manipur underscore the region's complex socio-economic and cultural landscape, shaped by a combination of indigenous practices and external influences.

2.2 Historical Development of Salt Wells in Manipur

Ningel: The Ningel Thumkhong, or Ningel brine well, has a storied history beginning with its initial excavation by Maharaja Puranthaba and the local people during his reign from 1247 to 1263 AD. Later, in 1736 AD, Maharaj Jayshree Garibniwaj

commissioned a new well and utilized a method called 'Thumkhong Hukpa,' which involved sinking and placing a wooden hollow cylinder to line the well. Further development occurred in early 1743. Maharaja Chingthangkhomba also dug the Ningel Thumkhong in 1782, establishing workers there to produce salt for offerings at the Shree Shree Govindajee Temple. Maharaja Chandrakriti expanded the brine wells at Ningel in 1862. Historically, Ningel was the largest salt market in Manipur until the reign of Maharaja Garibniwaj from 1709 to 1748. This prominence is confirmed by a stone pillar at Ningel engraved with 33 lines in Meitei Mayek, erected in 1658 Saka by Bamon Gangaram, which records a royal decree concerning the laws and practices for the villagers in the eastern valley.

Shikhong

The Shikhong brine well was initially developed by Moirang Yuthangba in February-March 1736 AD. Later, in January-February 1860, Sougajam Menjor, along with the Northern Tribes from regions like Ukhrul, Huining, Choithar, Haichum, and other Tangkhul offices, undertook further development of the well. The Shikhong brine well saw additional development in March-April 1865, as documented in the Cheitharol Kumbaba, the Court Chronicles of the kings of Manipur.

Chandrakhong

Chandrakhong's brine well was dug and developed by Maharaj Meidingu Chingthamkhomba in 1798 AD. He also established new villages around Chandrakhong to support salt production. Maharaja Bhagyachandra visited the site multiple times between 1793 and 1794. The Chandrakhong salt wells were destroyed by the Choithars (Tangkhuls) in 1799 but were restored starting in 1801 under the direction of Ebungshija Jagdanda Haobam and Keirungba Kumudananda. In 1805, Maharaja Chourajit oversaw the creation of seven new salt wells with help from the local Sekmai people. The Seven Years Devastation (1819-1826) led to a significant exodus of salt workers, but those from Sekmai continued production. Maharaja Gambhir Singh inspected the wells in 1832. Restoration and expansion efforts continued in 1855 under Maharaja Chandrakriti and others.

Waikhong

Waikhong saw significant activity as well. On February 1794, Ebungo Arambam Hajari and others led efforts to dig the Waikhong well. In 1805, Guru Masuthakur Anubananda further developed the area. In 1806, Yumnam Machungamba Hajari dug another well for the Royal Mother (Mama Shija). The practice of digging both public

and private brine wells persisted until the reign of Maharaj Budhachandra (1941-1955), during which the wells were known as "Tampakkhong." Today, salt is still produced for rituals such as the Umang Lai Haraoba, where offerings are made to forest deities.

Thiwa

Thiwa, a village in the Senapati District inhabited by the Tangkhuls, had three wells dug during the reign of Maharaja Naochinglen Nongdren Khomba (Chandrakirti) in 1886. Despite the interruption caused by the Second World War, salt production gradually resumed post-war.

Maharaj Chandrakirti established many salts well in the hill areas of Manipur to make self-sufficient. Thiwa is one of them. Maharaja Chandrakirti Singh K. C.S. I, during the reign of Naochinglen Nongtren Khomba Maharaj, Shri Kangbamcha Thangal Tulinaha Saheb was the General and his son Yaima Lalup made three saltwell in 1886. The surrounding of the saltwell was made fencing. Salt was produced till Second world War.

Fig 2.1: Thiwa Stone inscription indicating a thumkhong(source of salt) during the reign of Chandrakirti Maharaja (1886 AD)

Chibujang: Chibujang, located near the Indo-Myanmar border in the Churachandpur district, is noted in the Cheitharol Kumbaba for its brine wells. Four stone pillars were erected, featuring engravings of contributors' names and images. Key figures involved included Shribalaram Singh, Ahallup Lakpa Tulihal Major, and others.

2.2 Geographical Origins

Natural Brine Sources:

The geographical conditions of Manipur are ideal for traditional salt production. The state's topography, characterized by hills, valleys, and numerous natural springs, provides the perfect environment for harvesting brine. Salt springs are found in districts like Thoubal, Imphal, and Ukhrul, where the mineral-rich brine is extracted from natural sources. These areas are known for their specific geological formations that influence the brine's mineral content, contributing to the unique characteristics of Meitei Thum.

Environmental Conditions:

Manipur's climate plays a crucial role in the traditional salt-making process. The region's temperature variations and humidity levels impact the evaporation rate and the quality of the salt produced. Traditional methods rely on these environmental factors to achieve the desired crystallization of salt. The alignment of environmental conditions with traditional practices ensures that Meitei Thum retains its distinctive qualities and flavor.

Sustainable Practices:

Sustainability is a key aspect of traditional Meitei Thum production. The methods used are designed to minimize environmental impact and conserve natural resources. The reliance on natural brine sources and manual techniques reflects an ecological balance that has been maintained for centuries. Sustainable practices in Meitei Thum production include careful management of brine sources, minimal waste, and the preservation of natural habitats. These practices ensure the longevity of both the traditional methods and the natural resources they depend on.

2.3 Evolution Over Time

Historical Developments: In the Meitei dialect, common salt is generally known as "Thum" or "Chi." Traditional salt, produced locally in cake form, is referred to as "Meitei thumpak." Historically, salt cakes were used as currency in various regions, including Ethiopia, parts of Africa, and Tibet. In the Roman army, soldiers received an allowance of salt, which later evolved into a monetary allowance called "solarium" (the root of the modern English word "salary").

In Manipur, salt was once highly valued and used as a reward from the Maharaja for heroic deeds. An ancient text, "Loiyam Shinyam" (The 12th Century Constitution),

outlines how rewards were distributed for capturing a tiger. Among ten hunters, only three received rewards:

1. The first received a parcel of paddy field and "Thum namma," which was equivalent to one hundred plates of common salt.
2. The second hunter received cloth ("Phimakhai phi") and salt.
3. The third received a portion of both salt and cloth.

Thus, salt was not only a valuable commodity but also a symbol of honor and achievement in historical Manipur.

Modern Challenges: The rise of industrially produced salt posed several challenges to traditional Meitei Thum production. Industrial salt, produced through large-scale, mechanized processes, became more accessible and affordable, reducing the demand for traditional salt. This shift impacted local producers and led to a decrease in traditional salt-making practices. Additionally, competition from cheaper, mass-produced salts threatened the economic viability of Meitei Thum production.

Resurgence and Revival: In response to the challenges posed by industrialization, there has been a resurgence of interest in traditional and artisanal products, including Meitei Thum. The growing consumer preference for organic and heritage foods has led to renewed efforts to revive traditional salt production methods. Local communities, cultural organizations, and researchers are actively involved in documenting and promoting Meitei Thum. This resurgence includes efforts to market Meitei Thum as a premium product and to educate consumers about its cultural and historical significance.

Documentation and Research

Research and documentation are critical for preserving the traditional methods of Meitei Thum production. Scholars, practitioners, and cultural organizations are engaged in studying the historical, cultural, and technical aspects of Meitei Thum. This includes documenting traditional techniques, researching the historical context of salt production, and preserving oral histories related to Meitei Thum. These efforts contribute to a deeper understanding of Meitei Thum and support its preservation and promotion.

2.4 Meitei Thum in Traditional Practices

Brine Collection: The collection of natural brine is the first step in the production of Meitei Thum. Traditional methods involve gathering brine from salt springs and wells

located in specific geographical areas. The brine is collected using traditional tools and techniques that have been passed down through generations. The selection of brine sources is based on their mineral content and quality, ensuring that the salt produced retains its unique characteristics.

Boiling and Evaporation

The boiling and evaporation process is a labor-intensive stage in the production of Meitei Thum. The collected brine is boiled in large, open pots or pans, with careful management of temperature and evaporation rates. Traditional techniques are used to ensure even evaporation and prevent burning. The goal is to achieve the optimal crystallization of salt, which requires skill and experience. The boiling process is often monitored closely to ensure the quality of the salt.

Harvesting and Storage

After the brine has evaporated, the crystallized salt is carefully harvested. The salt is then stored in traditional containers, such as woven baskets or clay jars, to maintain its purity and quality. Proper storage is essential for preserving the salt's flavor and preventing contamination. Traditional containers are designed to protect the salt from external elements and ensure that it remains in optimal condition.

Cultural Rituals

The production of Meitei Thum is often accompanied by cultural rituals and practices. These rituals may include offerings to deities, prayers, and ceremonies that honor the traditional methods of salt production. Such practices reflect the spiritual significance of Meitei Thum and its role in the community. Rituals may be performed before, during, or after the production process, highlighting the integration of cultural and spiritual elements in the salt-making tradition.

Integration into Daily Life Meitei Thum is an integral part of daily life in the Meitei community. It is used in a variety of traditional dishes and culinary practices, adding unique flavor and enhancing the taste of food. The continued use of Meitei Thum in traditional cuisine underscores its importance in maintaining cultural traditions and culinary heritage. The salt is also valued for its role in food preservation, contributing to the sustainability of traditional food practices.

CHAPTER 3

PRODUCTION OF MEITEI THUM

The production of Meitei Thum involves a complex interplay of traditional craftsmanship and modern innovations. Traditional methods rely on natural ingredients, artisanal techniques, and cultural practices, producing a high-quality and unique product. Modern methods enhance efficiency, consistency, and scalability, but may impact the traditional qualities and sustainability of the production process. Addressing challenges such as raw material availability and the preservation of traditional knowledge is crucial for ensuring the sustainability and cultural significance of Meitei Thum. By integrating the strengths of both traditional and modern methods, the future of Meitei Thum can be preserved and celebrated while meeting contemporary demands.

3.1 Traditional Methods

The traditional methods of producing Meitei Thum have been passed down through generations, preserving the cultural and historical essence of this unique fermented fish product. These methods reflect the ingenuity and resourcefulness of the Meitei people, utilizing locally available resources and natural processes. This section delves into the traditional methods of producing Meitei Thum, detailing the ingredients, process, and tools and techniques involved. The traditional methods of producing

Fig 3.1: Ningel - Natural Salt Factory

Meitei Thum are a testament to the cultural heritage and culinary ingenuity of the Meitei people. These methods, which involve natural ingredients, manual techniques, and sensory monitoring, have been refined over centuries to create a product that is not only a staple in the local diet but also a symbol of cultural identity. Preserving

these traditional methods is crucial for maintaining the authenticity and uniqueness of Meitei Thum, even as modern techniques and market demands evolve.

3.1.1 Ingredients

The production of Meitei Thum traditionally involves a deep understanding of natural resources:

Natural Brine: The primary ingredient is brine sourced from natural salt springs and wells. These sources are carefully selected for their mineral content, which significantly impacts the salt's quality and flavor. The brine's composition varies based on the geological characteristics of the region, contributing to the unique qualities of Meitei Thum.

Traditional Additives: While not common, some producers may use local herbs or natural additives to enhance the salt's flavor or impart specific health benefits. These additives are used in small quantities to complement the salt's natural properties.

Fuel: Traditional methods use wood or biomass as fuel for the boiling process. This choice of fuel is not only sustainable but also aligns with the natural and cultural aspects of Meitei Thum production.

3.1.2 Process

The traditional process of making Meitei Thum is meticulous and involves several detailed steps:

Brine Collection: The process begins with the careful collection of brine from selected salt springs and wells. Collectors use traditional tools such as bamboo containers or clay pots to gather the brine, ensuring that it remains uncontaminated and retains its natural mineral composition. The knowledge of the best times and conditions for collection is often passed down through generations.

Boiling and Evaporation: The collected brine is poured into large, shallow pots or pans, typically made from clay or metal. These pots are placed over open fires, where the brine is heated to a controlled temperature to facilitate evaporation. The boiling process requires constant attention to ensure that the heat is evenly distributed and that the brine does not burn. This stage is crucial for the formation of high-quality salt crystals.

Crystallization: As the water evaporates, salt crystals begin to form on the surface of the brine. Artisans closely monitor this crystallization process, making adjustments to the heat and stirring the brine as necessary to promote even crystal formation. The

crystals are carefully harvested at the right moment to ensure they have the desired texture and purity.

Harvesting and Storage: Once crystallized, the salt is harvested using traditional tools. It is then dried and stored in containers such as woven baskets or clay jars. These containers are chosen for their ability to protect the salt from moisture and impurities, preserving its quality until it is ready for use or sale.

3.1.3 Tools and Techniques

Traditional Meitei Thum production employs specific tools and techniques:

Salt making tools hold a significant place in traditional salt production, reflecting the ingenuity and resourcefulness of communities that have perfected these methods over generations. Here is a detailed description of these traditional tools used in salt making:

1. Ishaiphu: This is a specialized vessel utilized during the collection of fresh salt water from wells. The design of the ishaiphu ensures that it can efficiently scoop and hold the brine, a crucial first step in the salt-making process. The vessel's shape and material are typically adapted to the local environment, ensuring durability and effectiveness in carrying out its function.

2. Thum Kagok: An iron pan locally crafted from sheets of coal drums, the Thum Kagok serves a vital role in the evaporation process. Historically, earthen pans were used before the advent of metalworking in the region. This transition from earthenware to iron reflects technological advancements and a shift towards more durable and heat-conductive materials, improving the efficiency of salt production.

3. Tei: The Tei is a flat, circular tray made of iron, used for shaping salt into cakes. This tool ensures that the salt takes on a uniform and compact shape, making it easier to handle, store, and transport. The precision in shaping is crucial as it influences the quality and marketability of the final product.

4. Koret: A large spoon made from a dried gourd, the Koret is used for pouring and stirring salt water. Its lightweight and heat-resistant properties make it ideal for handling hot brine during the boiling process. The use of natural materials like gourd highlights the sustainable practices embedded in traditional salt making.

5. Meiphei: A wooden device designed to maintain the temperature of the firewood hearth, the Meiphei plays a crucial role in regulating heat. This spade-like tool, equipped with a long wooden shaft, allows the operator to control the intensity of the

fire by manipulating hot charcoals within the hearth. This precise temperature control is essential for achieving optimal evaporation rates and ensuring consistent salt quality.

6. Chilel: An essential tool made from a brass plate with a wooden handle, the Chilel is used to shape salt into cakes. The craftsmanship of the Chilel is notable, with a single family of metal workers in Yairipok town traditionally responsible for its production. The legacy of making Chilel, passed down through generations, underscores the cultural heritage and specialized skills involved in salt making.

7. Chilengkhum: This earthen vessel is used to store plain water, serving as a cooling agent for the Chilel. Salt makers dip the heated Chilel into the Chilengkhum to cool it down after continuous use, preventing the brass plate from becoming too hot to handle and ensuring it maintains its shape and effectiveness.

8. Kambi: An earthen plate used to collect precipitated salt after evaporation. The Kambi's design allows for easy collection and transfer of the crystallized salt, facilitating the subsequent stages of drying and shaping.

9. Chegai: A piece of potsherd used for scraping the rim of salt cakes, the Chegai ensures that each salt cake has a smooth and finished appearance. This final touch not only enhances the aesthetic appeal but also prevents crumbling and loss of salt during handling.

10. Shapa: A wooden stamp used to mark salt cakes with a unique identifier, the Shapa is employed in a process called shapa namba. Each salt-making shed has a distinct Shapa design, allowing the origin of the salt to be easily identified. This practice of marking ensures traceability and authenticity of the salt, which is important for both quality control and maintaining the reputation of the salt makers. These tools and their respective roles in the salt-making process illustrate a sophisticated and well-organized system, developed through centuries of practice. Each tool is designed with specific functions in mind, contributing to the overall efficiency and quality of traditional salt production.

3.2 Method of Preparation

Commercial salt is manufactured from rock salt and from seawater and other natural and artificial brines. Artificial brines are typically created by pumping water into underground salt beds. In industrialized countries, a significant amount of brine is used directly (Encyclopedia Britannica, Vol.16, 1977:194).

Traditional Salt Making

The method of preparing salt involves the artificial evaporation method, where salt water is boiled in an open oven. The process traditionally engages women, though men are not prohibited from participating. Men often gather firewood and plantain leaves, crucial for the process. A typical salt-making shed requires at least six participants:

1. **Eeshing Kabi:** Fetches salt water from the well.
2. **Mei Thabi:** Controls the firing of the hearth.
3. **Thum Shabi:** Makes the salt.

Eeshing Kaba is the process of fetching and storing fresh salt water from the well in large earthen pitchers. The task is typically performed by women, though menstruating women are taboo from participating. The well site is sacred and considered the abode of the goddess Thumkhong Lairembi.

Mei Thabi manages the hearth's temperature using a tool called Meiphei. Fresh salt water is poured into pans placed over larger holes in the hearth, boiled until a preliminary concentration is noticed. The concentrated water is then transferred to another pan with the help of Koret (a dry gourd spoon), where it undergoes further heating (Khang Yenthokpa). As the water boils, white bubbles indicate the proper temperature has been reached.

Thum Shabi are essential in the traditional salt-making process in Ningel village, responsible for shaping and finishing the salt. After the salt is concentrated and collected in earthen plates, Thum Shabi transfer it to circular iron trays lined with plantain leaves, where they mold it into cakes using Chilens. They then stamp the cakes with wooden marks for identification and smooth the edges with potsherds (Chegai). Their expertise ensures that the salt is properly shaped for various uses, from daily consumption to ceremonial offerings, preserving both the quality and cultural significance of the salt.

The concentrated salt is collected in an earthen plate (Kambi) and shaped into cakes by the salt makers sitting at Phambal. Salt is shaped on circular iron trays (Tei) over smaller hearth holes, with plantain leaves lining the tray's surface. Chilens are used to shape the salt cakes, which are then stamped with a wooden mark for identification. The cakes are finished by rubbing the edges with Chegai (potsherds)

3.3 Types and Uses of Locally Manufactured Salt Cakes in Manipur

The salt cakes produced by Meitei salt makers in Manipur come in various shapes and sizes, each tailored for specific purposes. Here is a detailed look at the different types and their uses:

1. Thumjao

Thumjao is the largest salt cake produced in Manipur. It is plate-shaped with an undulated upper surface and a significant inner rim formed by a circular pit at the center. The margin is broad, and the edge gently tapers towards the bottom.

Uses: Thumjao is primarily used as an item of offering during ancestral worship and marriage ceremonies. Its large size makes it suitable for significant religious and cultural events where offerings are made to deities or ancestors.

2. Thum Talak

Thum Talak is slightly smaller than Thumjao. It also features a central depression, but this is smaller than that of Thumjao. The edge is not as broad as Thumjao.

Uses: This type of salt cake is mainly used for consumption. It is commonly found in households for daily cooking and seasoning.

3. Thum Samer

Thum Samer is characterized by a small ring of depression at the central surface and a thin edge. The margin from the inner ring to the outer edge is broad.

Uses: Thum Samer is primarily used for religious occasions and rituals, such as Yupan thaba, Shrada ceremony, Phiroi (death anniversary), and Shida thinba. It is often included in rituals that require offerings to ancestors or deities.

4. Thum Koiga

Thum Koiga is a plain salt cake without a central depression or inner ring. The edge of the outer circumference is thick.

Uses: This type of salt cake is mainly used for household consumption. It is a versatile salt used in everyday cooking. The fine qualities of Koiga are specifically utilized in preparing food for women who have recently given birth and are in a pollution period, indicating its importance in postpartum care.

5. Thum Macha

Thum Macha is the smallest form of salt cake produced by Meitei salt makers. It has a surface diameter of about 7 inches and features a central depression forming an inner circle on the surface.

Uses: Thum Macha is used in various auspicious occasions, feasts, and festivals, such as Shajibu Cheiraoba (Meitei New Year) and Lamtai thangja. It is also used in rituals involving ancestral worship. Despite its small size, its ceremonial importance is significant, often used in rituals that mark important cultural and religious milestones. Each type of salt cake is crafted with specific cultural, religious, and practical purposes in mind, reflecting the rich traditions and customs of the Meitei people in Manipur.

3.4 Modern Methods

While traditional methods of producing Meitei Thum have been preserved and celebrated, modern techniques have been introduced to enhance efficiency, ensure consistency, and meet growing market demands. This section explores these modern methods, comparing them with traditional practices, and discussing innovations that have been adopted in recent times. The integration of modern methods in the production of Meitei Thum has brought about significant improvements in efficiency, consistency, and marketability. While these innovations offer numerous benefits, it is crucial to balance them with the preservation of traditional practices and cultural heritage. By adopting modern techniques thoughtfully and sustainably, producers can ensure the continued relevance and success of Meitei Thum in a competitive market.

3.4.1 Innovations

Modern methods of producing Meitei Thum have introduced several innovations to enhance efficiency and scalability:

Mechanized Evaporation: Modern production facilities use mechanized systems for evaporating brine. These systems involve evaporation tanks and controlled heat sources, such as electric heaters or gas burners, which allow for faster and more consistent evaporation. This mechanization increases production capacity and reduces labor intensity.

Filtration and Purification: Advanced filtration technologies are employed to remove impurities from the brine before it is boiled. These filtration systems ensure that the brine is of the highest quality, free from contaminants, and safe for consumption. Purification processes help in achieving consistent product quality.

Quality Control: Modern methods incorporate rigorous quality control measures. Laboratory testing is conducted to analyze the mineral content, purity, and safety of

the salt. These tests help ensure that the final product meets industry standards and regulatory requirements.

Packaging and Branding: Innovations in packaging, such as vacuum-sealed bags and moisture-proof containers, improve the shelf life of Meitei Thum and protect it from environmental factors. Branding efforts emphasize the cultural heritage and unique qualities of the salt, appealing to modern consumers who value authenticity and tradition.

3.4.2 Comparison with Traditional Methods

Comparing traditional and modern methods highlights several key differences and benefits:

Efficiency: Modern methods are significantly more efficient, enabling higher production volumes and faster processing times. Mechanized systems and controlled environments reduce the labor and time required for production.

Quality and Authenticity: Traditional methods produce salt with unique flavors and textures, reflecting the natural environment and cultural practices. Modern methods prioritize consistency and scalability, but may not capture the artisanal qualities and nuanced flavors of traditionally produced Meitei Thum.

Sustainability: Traditional methods emphasize sustainable practices and minimal environmental impact. Modern methods, while efficient, may require more energy and resources, potentially affecting their sustainability. Balancing modern efficiency with traditional sustainability is essential for long-term production.

3.5 External Trade of Salt

The state of Manipur produced enough salt on its own during the precolonial era. Salt was not imported nor exported by the state. However, shortly after 1891, Manipur's formerly independent salt industry began to rely more on Assamese and other neighboring kingdoms. The main causes were the accessibility of inexpensive, premium Liverpool salt, the British government's indifference to the scientific and strategic advancement of the state's salt industry, social unrest and political unpredictability, privatization of salt wells, commercialization of markets, and shifts in consumer tastes and preferences. Gambhir Singh and the British government signed a pact on April 18, 1833, which states that the Rajah "will in no way obstruct the trade carried on between the two countries by Bengali or Munipooree (Manipuri) merchants." According to Aitchison (1909: 267), "He will not impose heavy duties

and he will create a monopoly of any kind of merchandise." Thus, the British gained control of the salt business and financial administration. The manufacturing volume was not able to keep up with the expanding salt market.

Consumer preferences had shift: They admitted that they preferred foreign salt over native salt. One of the main factors leading to a rise in the import of Liverpool white salt was the advancement of transportation after the Palace Rebellion in 1891. The imported salt was bought and consumed without reluctance by the hill tribes, but it was viewed with distrust by the valley people due to caste stereotypes (Haokip 2019: 259). With better transportation, the price of imported salt decreased, while the cost of salt produced locally went up due to a lack of fuel and labor.

Following 1891, when the Manipur state was fully subjugated by the British under the terms of the Sanad of 1891, a significant amount and value of salt was shipped from Assam into Manipur.

Until then, there was no salt import or export between Assam and Manipur between 1876–1878 and 1890–1891, with the exception of 1877–1878 and 1890–1891 when Assam exported salt to Manipur at ~3 and ~4, respectively (RAPA 1877–78: xcv–69; RAPA 1892–93: cxi–81). Manipur imported 237 maunds of salt worth around 1,087 total during the 1892–1893 year. The amount of salt fell to 51 maunds, valued at about 248, in 1893–1894. As previously mentioned, during periods of shortage, a limited amount of salt was sporadically imported from Burma and Cachar, Assam (Brown 1874: 9). However, according to RAPA 1876–77: 84, "the major portion of the transactions in connection with the trade between this Province and Manipur [took] place at the annual fair held at Silchar" during the 1880s.

As a result, Manipur, which had previously relied on its own economy for the manufacture of salt, became a needy economy.

3.6 Challenges in Production

Meitei Thum production has a number of issues that have an impact on its sustainability, quality, and economic feasibility. Understanding these problems is critical for devising ways that retain conventional practices while adjusting to current expectations. This section delves into the fundamental obstacles of producing Meitei Thum, such as raw material availability, the preservation of traditional knowledge,

and environmental and economic constraints. The problems in producing Meitei Thum are diverse, encompassing environmental, cultural, and economic considerations. Addressing these difficulties needs a comprehensive strategy that incorporates sustainable methods, traditional knowledge preservation, and producer assistance. By addressing these concerns, Meitei Thum production may be sustained and improved, assuring its continuing cultural and economic value.

3.6.1 Raw Material Availability

Availability of high-quality raw materials poses several challenges:

Brine Sources: Natural salt springs and wells are vital for Meitei Thum production. However, these sources are susceptible to environmental changes, pollution, and over-extraction. Protecting and managing these sources sustainably is crucial for maintaining the quality and availability of brine.

Environmental Impact: Changes in land use, water management practices, and climate conditions can affect the availability and quality of brine sources. Implementing sustainable extraction practices and mitigating environmental impacts are essential to preserve these resources.

3.6.2 Preservation of Traditional Knowledge

Preserving traditional knowledge and skills is critical for maintaining the cultural heritage of Meitei Thum:

Generational Knowledge Transfer: Ensuring that traditional salt-making techniques are passed down through generations is essential. This involves documenting methods, providing training to younger generations, and supporting local artisans to continue traditional practices.

Economic Viability: Traditional producers face financial challenges when competing with industrial salt production. Supporting traditional methods sustainably and economically is possible through encouraging fair-trade practices, enhancing market access, and educating consumers. These efforts can help preserve cultural heritage and ensure the livelihood of traditional salt producers.

Cultural Integration: Balancing traditional knowledge with current breakthroughs necessitates a courteous approach that values cultural history while welcoming positive improvements. Collaboration among communities, scholars, and governments is required to strike this balance and encourage the preservation of traditional traditions.

CHAPTER 4

CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF MEITEI THUM

Meitei Thum holds profound cultural significance for the Meitei people, encompassing religious, medicinal, culinary, social, and economic dimensions. Its role in traditional practices and its symbolic value underscore the importance of preserving and promoting this unique aspect of Meitei heritage. By maintaining these traditions, the Meitei community not only preserves its cultural identity but also supports sustainable livelihoods and fosters a sense of pride and continuity.

4.1 Symbolism and Meaning

Meitei Thum carries profound symbolic meanings within the Meitei culture:

Purity and Protection: Salt is universally considered a purifying agent. In Meitei culture, it is believed to cleanse spaces and ward off negative energies. Sprinkling salt around homes and during rituals symbolizes the removal of impurities and protection from evil forces. This practice is deeply rooted in the belief that salt can absorb negative influences and provide a barrier against harm.

Prosperity and Well-being: Salt is often associated with prosperity and well-being. It is believed to attract positive energy and bring good fortune to households. This belief is reflected in various cultural practices where salt is used to symbolize wealth and abundance.

Cultural Identity: Meitei Thum represents the rich cultural heritage of the Meitei people. The traditional methods of producing and using Meitei Thum reflect the community's deep connection to their land and natural resources. This traditional knowledge and practice are integral to the cultural identity and continuity of the Meitei people.

4.2 Role in Festivals and Ceremonies

Meitei Thum is integral to various festivals and ceremonies, underscoring its cultural significance:

Religious Festivals: During major religious festivals such as Lai Haraoba, Emoinu Irapa which celebrates the creation myth and honors the deities of the Meitei pantheon, salt is used in offerings to deities. It is believed to purify the offerings, making them acceptable to the gods and ensuring the success of the rituals. The use of salt in these ceremonies highlights its role as a sacred substance.

Lairharaoba: Meitei thum (salt) is used in *lairharaoba*, there is a ritual on the first day of *Lai Ekouba*. It is an act of invocation of the spirit of the deities from nearby water (a pond or a river). All the participants of the *Lai Ekouba* are lined up in a certain order. An auspicious time is set in the afternoon, intended for the progress and prosperity of the community. On reaching the precincts of the shrine *Mei-Okpa* (greeting with fire) by burning *khoiju* herbs (*Plectranthus ternifolius*) with Meitei thum (salt) and other rituals are done and the procession walked towards the Shrine.

Emoinu Iratpa: *Emoinu Ahongbi* (alias *Emoinu Ahong Achaubi*) as another form of Goddess *Leimarel Sidabi*. *Leimarel Sidabi* is the supreme mother. *Emoinu* is regarded as an ever-resourceful lady. She always gives wealth and prosperity to the mankind. She was shown as having a human appearance. She resides near the fire hearth. The goddess is believed to be the controller and regulator of good conduct and behavior of the human beings. *Ebendhou Emoinu* is offered from the first serving of every meal prepared in a Meitei household. The serving is made by placing three servings of the cooked rice on a plate that is set aside. To please *Emoinu*, the offerings should include only vegetarian foods or fish, and Meitei Thum (salt). Household members are also expected to maintain discipline, be respectful, and keep their surroundings tidy.

Housewarming Ceremonies: In ceremonies marking the completion of a home, salt is sprinkled around the house to purify the space and protect it from negative influences. This practice is a manifestation of the belief that salt can create a protective barrier against evil spirits and bring prosperity to the new household.

Life Cycle Events: Meitei Thum is integral to ceremonies marking significant life events, including births, weddings, and funerals. For example, during wedding ceremonies, salt is often exchanged between families as a symbol of harmony and prosperity. This exchange signifies the merging of two families and the wish for a prosperous future. The importance of salt in the Manipuri culture can thus be known from the keen efforts of the rulers and the people to find and develop salt springs in the hills and the valley of Manipur over the centuries. Salt is not only an item used in food items, but also an integral ingredient in ritualistic practices and social events. Even today, only Meitei Thum is used for religious offerings, and not the salt produced from outside Manipur. Salt is also an indispensable item in the various rites of passage like birth, wedding, and death ceremonies. As a customary ritual, three plates of salt and some pine woods are brought from the parental house of a woman when she is around seven months pregnant.

When a woman gives birth, she is usually given only Meitei salt in her diet. During the birth ritual of Ipan Thaba, Meitei salt is a must. During a wedding ceremony, phiruk nungshang is an important ritual for which the Meitei salt is required. The religious ritual of Saroi Khangba, which is performed in the month of Lamta, also requires this salt.

Healing Rituals: Salt is used in traditional healing rituals to cleanse the body and spirit. It is often combined with other natural elements in practices designed to restore health and balance. These healing rituals underscore the belief in salt's purifying and protective properties.

4.3 Rewards and Recognitions

The Royal Chronical Cheitharol Kumbaba contains many instances of salt being given as an award. In 1841-1844, the people of Hungkun Thokchom and Sekmai had a Khupak ishei (musical concert), and Sekmai won the khupak ishei. Fifty flat salt cakes and ten lakh sen were given to them as a reward

Two Kom tribe members were rewarded with two pieces of palmanquin clothes and a basket of salt in 1847 for snatching thieves.

During the Sajibu Cheiraoba and Cheithaba rituals at the royal palace, it remains customary to reward the individual designated as the cheithaba for the year with Meitei salt. This tradition has been observed continuously since the time of King Kiyamba.

Fig 4.1: A salt is rewarded to a person who is assigned as Cheithaba

4.4 Punishments and Penalties

Anti-social elements and people who lied to the Maharajas would be punished by exiling them to work at faraway brine wells.

Two men were sent to work at the brine wells of Pallel in April 1734 AD for lying to the Maharaja. In the Saka era 1769 (AD 1847) on the 6th of Sajibu, Monday, when Akoijam Kriti asked Wahengbam Maichou to pay the price of a boat, the latter along with his son Chaoba and two servants threw the former into the water of Pukhramba Thinglen. Akoijam Kriti was rescued by the servant of Eroiba Khutheiba Hanjaba when the latter was sailing paddy in a boat. Upon inquiry, it was revealed that Wahengba was responsible for the crime. Wahengba was later exiled to Chandrakhong.

In 1836 Tongbram pebam was found to have thrown a written paper into the Royal Palace he was made to become a labour in the salt mine

Ebungshija Khwairakpa visited Leishangkhong to offer prayers in 1853 AD. Umanglais (forest deities) such as Sanamahi and Ebudhou Pakhangba were not prayed to by members of the royal family as a tradition. By praying to the umlais, he was trying to dethrone the Maharaja and become the Maharaja himself. Yumnam Luchon was later exiled to Ningel.

4.5 Meitei Thum in Daily Life

In daily life, Meitei Thum is indispensable for the Meitei people:

Culinary Uses: As a fundamental ingredient in Manipuri cuisine, Meitei Thum is used to season various dishes, enhancing their flavor. It is especially important in preparing traditional foods like 'Ngari' (fermented fish) and 'Soibum' (fermented bamboo shoots), which are staples in the Meitei diet. The distinct taste of Meitei Thum, derived from its unique mineral content, sets Manipuri cuisine apart.

Food Preservation: Salt's preservative properties make it vital for storing food. It is used in pickling vegetables and fruits, a common practice in Manipuri households. This method of preservation not only extends the shelf life of food but also adds a distinctive flavor, contributing to the unique culinary traditions of the Meitei people.

Medicinal Uses: In traditional medicine, Meitei Thum is used to treat digestive issues, skin conditions, and respiratory ailments. Its mineral content is believed to have healed properties, making it a valuable component in various remedies. For instance,

saltwater gargles are used for sore throats, and salt scrubs are applied to the skin for their therapeutic benefits.

Agricultural Practices: Salt is occasionally used in traditional agricultural practices to improve soil fertility and enhance crop yields. It is also added to animal feed to promote livestock health. These practices highlight the multifunctional use of salt in rural communities, contributing to sustainable agricultural practices.

Household Protection: Beyond ceremonies, small amounts of salt are kept in homes as a continuous protection measure. This practice, which involves placing salt in corners or at entrances, symbolizes ongoing vigilance against negative energies and misfortune. It reflects the enduring belief in the protective power of salt.

CHAPTER 5

CONTEMPORARY RELEVANCE AND USAGE

Meitei Thum remains relevant in contemporary times due to its unique cultural, culinary, and economic significance. The expansion of commercial production and market dynamics reflect its growing demand and potential. Government and non-governmental efforts are crucial for cultural preservation and promotion, ensuring that traditional practices are sustained and valued. While challenges such as regulatory issues and the need for sustainable practices exist, they also present opportunities for innovation and growth. Cultural tourism, in particular, offers a promising avenue for enhancing the visibility and appreciation of Meitei Thum, contributing to both cultural preservation and economic development.

5.1 Meitei Thum in Modern Times

In the context of modern society, Meitei Thum continues to hold significant cultural and economic value despite the proliferation of industrially manufactured salt. This traditional salt from Manipur, India, is not only a staple in the regional cuisine but also a symbol of the Meitei people's rich heritage. The contemporary relevance of Meitei Thum can be understood through several dimensions:

Cultural Resurgence: There is a growing global trend towards valuing artisanal and traditional products. Consumers increasingly seek authenticity and a connection to heritage, which has led to a renewed interest in Meitei Thum. This resurgence is partly fueled by a broader movement towards sustainability and organic products, positioning Meitei Thum as an example of traditional craftsmanship that aligns with modern values of environmental stewardship and cultural preservation.

Adaptation and Innovation: Modern producers are adapting traditional practices to meet contemporary demands. Innovations in packaging, such as eco-friendly materials and attractive designs, aim to appeal to both local and international markets. Additionally, the development of online platforms and e-commerce is helping producers reach a wider audience, making Meitei Thum accessible to consumers beyond the region.

Health and Wellness Trends: With increasing awareness about health and wellness, there is a growing appreciation for natural and mineral-rich products. Meitei Thum, known for its unique mineral composition, is being recognized for its potential health

benefits. This trend supports its position as a valuable alternative to conventional salt, emphasizing its natural origin and artisanal production.

The Medicinal Benefits of Brine Salt Consumption: Recent scientific research has revealed numerous medicinal benefits associated with the consumption of pure brine salt. The mineral composition and concentration of ions present in brine salt have shown positive effects such as mucolysis, reduction in inflammation, improved asthma control, decreased COPD exacerbations, relief from asthma and allergy-related symptoms, and stimulation of the immune system (Zajac et al, 2020).

Utilizing Brine Salt as a Food Preservative: In addition to its medicinal benefits, brine salt also serves as an excellent food preservative. With the advancement of scientific approaches, the brine salt produced in Manipur can be utilized in the food industry. By leveraging modern packaging technologies, the production capacity of brine salt can be boosted, supporting the revival of the industry in the state. This not only provides economic opportunities for the salt-making villages but also helps meet the growing demand for natural and preservative-free food products.

Brine Salt Springs and Mineral Exploration: Interestingly, brine salt springs in Manipur have been identified as potential sources of brine salt deposited with the increasing demand for lithium in the electric vehicle industry, the exploration and extraction of lithium from brine salt springs present a new opportunity for economic growth (Samadiy et.al, 2020). By investing in mineral exploration, Manipur can tap into this valuable resource and contribute to the global demand for lithium.

5.2 Economic Impact

The economic impact of Meitei Thum is multifaceted, involving aspects of commercialization, market dynamics, and local economic contributions. While the transition to commercial production has opened new opportunities and increased revenue for producers, challenges such as supply chain issues and competition need to be addressed to ensure the continued success and sustainability of Meitei Thum in the market.

5.2.1 Commercial Production:

The commercial production of Meitei Thum is evolving, with several key factors contributing to its economic impact:

Local Industry Development: Small-scale and cottage industries play a crucial role in the production of Meitei Thum. Local artisans and cooperatives are central to this

sector, often utilizing traditional methods passed down through generations. These producers benefit from a niche market that values artisanal and heritage products.

Economic Benefits: The commercialization of Meitei Thum creates significant economic opportunities for local communities. By engaging in the production and sale of this traditional salt, producers generate income, support local economies, and contribute to rural development. The growth of this sector also helps in sustaining traditional livelihoods and practices.

Export and Global Reach: Efforts are being made to expand the market for Meitei Thum beyond local and national boundaries. Producers are exploring export opportunities to introduce Meitei Thum to international markets. By leveraging its unique qualities and traditional methods, there is potential to tap into global markets that appreciate artisanal and culturally significant products.

5.2.2 Market Dynamics

The market dynamics for Meitei Thum are influenced by various factors:

Local Demand: In Manipur, Meitei Thum is a cherished ingredient used in daily cooking and traditional recipes. The local market like Khwairamanband keithel and other market in the valley region remains a stronghold for this product, with consumers preferring it for its taste and cultural significance.

Regional and National Markets: Marketing strategies are being developed to introduce Meitei Thum to regional and national markets. This involves creating awareness about its unique attributes and health benefits. Producers are also working on branding and positioning Meitei Thum as a premium product, distinct from mass-produced alternatives.

International Opportunities: The potential for Meitei Thum to enter international markets is promising. Global consumers are increasingly seeking authentic and organic products, which aligns with the characteristics of Meitei Thum. Efforts to penetrate international markets involve understanding consumer preferences, navigating export regulations, and building distribution networks.

5.3 Cultural Preservation and Promotion

Cultural preservation and promotion of Meitei Thum involve a multifaceted approach that includes government support, non-governmental efforts, tourism development, and educational initiatives. By combining these efforts, the cultural heritage of Meitei

Thum can be safeguarded and celebrated, ensuring its continued relevance and appreciation in both local and global contexts.

5.3.1 Government Support and Policy Implications

Lack of Government Support: Despite the cultural and economic importance of Meitei Thum, there is a notable absence of adequate government support for traditional salt production. The lack of governmental intervention impacts various aspects of the industry, from production and marketing to preservation of traditional methods. Without sufficient support, producers face difficulties in competing with industrially produced salt and struggle to access necessary resources and markets.

The absence of government support means that the traditional salt producers must rely heavily on their own resources and community-driven initiatives. This lack of backing hinders the potential for growth and sustainability, making it challenging for the industry to thrive in a modern economic context.

Recommendations for Enhanced Support: To address the challenges posed by the lack of government support, it is essential to advocate for increased governmental involvement in the preservation and promotion of Meitei Thum. Recommendations include implementing policies that provide financial assistance to salt producers, supporting traditional production methods through subsidies, and investing in infrastructure improvements.

Furthermore, recognizing Meitei Thum as a valuable cultural asset can help garner the attention needed for greater support and investment. Enhanced government engagement can facilitate market expansion, improve production efficiency, and ensure the long-term sustainability of Meitei Thum production, thus preserving its cultural and economic significance for future generations.

Cultural Heritage Recognition: Governments at various levels play a crucial role in recognizing and preserving traditional practices like Meitei Thum. Initiatives may include recognizing Meitei Thum as a part of intangible cultural heritage, which can lead to funding and support for preservation efforts. Government agencies may work to document traditional methods and practices to ensure they are passed down to future generations.

Support for Traditional Practices: Government programs can provide financial support and resources to artisans and producers of Meitei Thum. Grants, subsidies, or low-interest loans can help maintain traditional production methods and improve

facilities. Support might also include training programs to help producers enhance their skills and adapt to modern market demands while preserving traditional techniques.

Cultural Festivals and Events: Governments should organize or support cultural festivals and events that highlight traditional foods, including Meitei Thum. These events provide a platform for showcasing Meitei Thum, attracting tourists, and educating the public about its cultural significance. Such festivals also offer opportunities for local producers to gain exposure and connect with consumers.

5.3.2 Non-Governmental Efforts

Community-Based Organizations: Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and community-based groups play an important role in the preservation and promotion of Meitei Thum. These organizations may work on projects that document traditional knowledge, promote sustainable production practices, and support local producers. They often collaborate with local communities to ensure that preservation efforts are culturally sensitive and effective.

Cultural Promotion Campaigns: NGOs and cultural organizations may run campaigns to raise awareness about Meitei Thum and its cultural significance. These campaigns can use various media platforms, including social media, documentaries, and print publications, to reach a wider audience. They may also organize educational workshops and seminars to teach about the history and production of Meitei Thum.

Partnerships with Educational Institutions: Collaborations with universities and research institutions can help preserve Meitei Thum through academic research and documentation. Projects might include studying traditional production methods, exploring historical records, and developing educational materials. These partnerships can also facilitate knowledge transfer and ensure that traditional practices are preserved and respected.

5.3.3 Promotion through Cultural Tourism

Tourism Development: Promoting Meitei Thum as part of cultural tourism can significantly contribute to its preservation. Developing tourism packages that include visits to traditional production sites, cooking demonstrations, and tastings can attract tourists and provide economic benefits to local communities. Tourism can create demand for Meitei Thum and support its continued production. Additionally, collaborating with local artisans and craftsmen can enhance the culture.

Culinary Tourism Initiatives: Culinary tourism initiatives can focus on Meitei Thum by including it in regional food tours, cooking classes, and food festivals. Showcasing Meitei Thum in this context highlights its cultural significance and provides tourists with an authentic culinary experience. Collaborations with chefs, food writers, and travel influencers can further promote Meitei Thum to a global audience.

Cultural Exchange Programs:

Participating in cultural exchange programs and international food fairs can introduce Meitei Thum to a broader audience. By sharing Meitei Thum with global culinary communities, producers can foster greater appreciation and understanding of this traditional food. These programs also create opportunities for learning and collaboration with other cultures.

5.3.4 Educational and Research Initiatives

Documentation and Archiving:

Documenting the history, production methods, and cultural significance of Meitei Thum is essential for its preservation. Archiving traditional recipes, techniques, and stories ensures that this knowledge is preserved for future generations. Research projects and publications can also contribute to the understanding and appreciation of Meitei Thum.

Educational Programs:

Educational programs focused on Meitei Thum can be implemented in schools and community centers. These programs can teach students and community members about the cultural heritage of Meitei Thum, including its history, production methods, and role in traditional practices. Engaging younger generations is crucial for ensuring the continuation of traditional knowledge.

Workshops and Training:

Organizing workshops and training sessions for producers and community members can help maintain traditional production techniques. These sessions can provide hands-on experience, share best practices, and offer guidance on how to adapt traditional methods to contemporary standards while preserving authenticity.

CHAPTER 6

NINGEL - A Lesser-Known Cultural Treasure

Ningel, a prominent cultural and historical site in Manipur, holds profound significance for the Meitei people. This chapter delves into the historical background, cultural practices, and modern challenges associated with Ningel, offering insights into its importance and the rituals surrounding it. As a key element of Manipuri heritage, Ningel exemplifies the rich tapestry of traditions and spiritual beliefs that characterize the region.

Ningel is approximately 25 kilometers (15.5 miles) from Imphal, the capital city of Manipur. The relatively short distance makes it accessible for visitors and locals alike, allowing for regular participation in cultural and religious activities held at the site. The proximity to Imphal also facilitates the integration of Ningel into the broader cultural and economic activities of the region. Despite its historical and cultural value, Ningel faces various contemporary challenges. The impact of modernization, changing lifestyles, and limited resources pose threats to the preservation of its traditional practices. Understanding these issues is crucial for developing strategies to maintain and promote Ningel's cultural significance while adapting to the needs of a modern society.

How salt wellsprings were erected at Ningel has its own story as narrated by village folk. It is said that during the reign of Maharaja Puranthaba, in the Lairam Tangkhul village neighbouring Ningel was a widow who reared a pig. Her pig was killed by a 'Ngaren' Khoi, a kind of bee and she had requested the village chief to help her catch the bee. The chief then had hired 10 strong and sturdy men from the neighbouring village of Lairam Funga, and the widow was told that she had to feed those 10 men. Those men proved futile even after a vigorous search and headed back. The first men who came back asked for some water to quench his thirst and the widow gave him spring water from a nearby hillock. The man burst with anger that the woman gave him poisonous water, he relayed it to those other men and one of them identified that it was the taste of 'noin' that is salt and not some poison. The widow took them to the place where she had fetched the water from and was decided that the presence of salt should be reported to the Maharaja and 'Utang' bamboo was planted to easily identify the spot.

The present salt wellspring at Ningel was dug and erected only by the successors of the then-Maharaja. The Maharaja also ordered that the widow of the Tangkhul community be made to take part in 'Lai Haraoba' ceremonies, not abiding by this will result in severe punishments. Thus were the close ties between Lairam Tangkhul village and Meitei Ningel village. Years later when the death of the widow was reported to the Maharaja, the Maharaja ordered those flowers from Lairam Tangkhul village be plucked and presented to the deities during the proceeding of 'Lai Haraoba' and rendering age old custom of equating flowers to women. Thus, even to the present day, a couple of days before the 'Lai Haraoba' that is the annual ceremonies of rites and rituals to please the gods, 20 sacks of salt will be sent to Lairam Tangkhul village asking his permission to let the Maharaja's men pluck flowers. The village chief will then distribute the salt discs to his villagers. The unmarried men and women of the village will pluck flowers which will be carried in a flower basket made by the village chief himself. The flowers are brought by those men and women towards Ningel village making sure no one crosses right in front of their procession on their way from Lairam Tangkhul village to Ningel village as customs have it. These are some of the stories and instances we have come across related to Meitei salt.

Now with globalization and westernization, many different salt brands have flooded the state, and the Meitei salt business has deteriorated, one important reason being the former is less expensive and easily available, thus resulting in the loss of the importance of traditional Meitei salt so much most youngsters are ignorant of what our traditional salt is. It is high time that we come together so that to some extent we may be able to safeguard this age-old custom of salt processing.

Traditional Salt Production Techniques

Khong (well) indicates the place of salt well. Thus, the word thum had been a cultural element that projects the socio-religious and economic strength of the the people of Manipur.

Thum Khong (Salt reservoir): Salt waters in the Ningel foothill are reserved and stored in the well-constructed by piercing a giant hollow wood of length about Lam mapanga makhai shangba i.e. 54Vi ft. in length. It is said that the wooden well was installed during the reign of Maharaj Chingthangkhomba, popularly known by Rajshree Bhagyachandra in the 18 century A.D. The site is believed to have been guarded by the goddess Thumkhong Lairembi who is venerated and given reverence by the villagers and the common people while visiting the site.

Thum-Shung-Shang (Salt Preparing Shed): The shed where salt is manufactured is known as Thum shung sang. It is a structure having three walls, raised out of bamboo mats or splits duly supported with bamboo or wooden poles. The roof of the shed is two sided and thatched with local grasses. The shed looks simply but is very effective in receiving maximum amount of wind.

Thum Leirang (Salt preparing Hearth/Kiln): Salt is prepared in a typical form of longitudinal hearth called thum leirang. It is a raised structure made out of clay having two openings, one in the front end and other in the rear end. The front opening or the mouth is called Chamang. It measures about 7 ft. in width and 1ft. in height. Fire wood is placed and set fire from this opening. The hearth comprises of circular holes of two different sizes called Kamit. These holes serve as oven upon which pan and trays are mounted. The larger holes in front of the hearth are mainly used for boiling the salt water whereas the succeeding smaller holes are used for giving the shape of the salt. The length of hearth varies from one to another depending upon the ability of the manufacturer that, how much quantity of salt makers he can afford. Normally, the breath & height of each hearth seems almost the same which is scales about 7 ft and 1 ft. The mouth of the hearth normally faces to such a direction, where it can receive maximum flow of wind for proper burning of fire. There are open spaces in two sides of the central hearth known as Phambal (space for the salt makers). Kharung (Earthen vessels for storing fresh salt water) La (plaintain leaves) and other tools are kept in this open space.

The rear opening of the hearth is called **Chaning**. The ashes of the burnt fuels are collected from this end which are stuffed and stored in a basket called Khari Polang. It is kept on a raised platform at the extreme corner of the two walls. It is used for obtaining

Khari ichum (liquid ashes) to prepare Khari (edible soda). Another wooden and bamboo platform built behind the hearth to a close proximity of the rear wall is called Lap yai which is mainly for stacking fire wood to be used as a fuel for making salt.

6.1 Historical Background of Ningel Thumkhong

Origins and Development:

Ningel's historical roots trace back to the early days of the Meitei civilization, serving as a central hub for cultural and spiritual activities. Historically, it has been a site

where significant events and rituals were conducted, reflecting its integral role in the community's cultural narrative. The evolution of Ningel over time highlights its enduring importance in the life of the Meitei people and its adaptation to changing social and political landscapes.

Over the centuries, Ningel has been associated with various historical events and figures, contributing to its rich historical tapestry. Its development reflects the broader history of Manipur, intertwining with the region's political, social, and religious transformations. This historical context provides a deeper understanding of Ningel's role in shaping and reflecting the Meitei identity.

Cultural and Religious Importance:

Ningel's cultural and religious significance is evident in its role as a site for numerous rituals and ceremonies. It is revered as a sacred space where the Meitei people conduct important cultural and spiritual practices, reinforcing its status as a vital component of their heritage. The site's association with traditional festivals and rites underscores its deep-rooted connection to the Meitei's spiritual beliefs and communal life.

The religious importance of Ningel is further highlighted by its use in various ceremonial practices. It serves as a focal point for activities that reinforce the community's spiritual values and cultural continuity. The reverence for Ningel reflects the broader cultural ethos of the Meitei people, emphasizing the significance of preserving such sacred sites to maintain the integrity of their traditions.

6.2 Traditional Practices and Rituals at Ningel Thumkhong

Ritual Cleansing Before Entering Ningel Thumkhong: A key tradition associated with Ningel is the ritual cleansing required before entering the site. Visitors must take a bath to purify themselves, ensuring that they approach the sacred space in a state of spiritual cleanliness. This practice highlights the deep respect and reverence for Ningel, reinforcing its sanctity and the importance of maintaining purity in the presence of sacred sites.

The ritual cleansing reflects broader cultural values of purity and respect within Meitei traditions. It underscores the belief that certain spaces, like Ningel, hold spiritual significance that demands a certain level of personal and ritual cleanliness. This practice not only preserves the sanctity of Ningel but also reinforces the cultural and spiritual discipline of the community.

Restrictions on Leather Products: At Ningel, entering while wearing leather products such as shoes and slippers is strictly prohibited. This restriction is rooted in cultural beliefs that consider leather items to be impure. By enforcing this rule, the community maintains the sacredness of Ningel and adheres to traditional practices that reflect their spiritual and cultural values.

The prohibition of leather products is a manifestation of the broader cultural taboos associated with sacred spaces. It highlights the intricate relationship between material objects and spiritual beliefs in Meitei culture. This practice ensures that the integrity of Ningel is preserved, reflecting the community's commitment to upholding traditional values and maintaining the purity of their sacred sites.

Restrictions for Bereaved Families: In the event of a family member's death, the bereaved family is not allowed to enter Ningel. This restriction is based on cultural beliefs related to mourning and purity, acknowledging that the period of mourning is a time of spiritual separation. It underscores the respect for the sanctity of the site and the community's adherence to spiritual and cultural norms.

This practice reflects the broader cultural understanding of purity and ritual separation during periods of grief. By observing such restrictions, the community upholds the sanctity of Ningel and maintains the spiritual discipline associated with sacred spaces. This section delves into the cultural and spiritual reasons behind these restrictions and their role in preserving the integrity of Ningel.

Cultural Use of Salt from Ningel During Pregnancy: The salt produced at Ningel is highly valued, not only for its cultural significance but also for its practical uses, particularly during pregnancy. It is traditionally consumed for its believed health benefits, including aiding digestion and providing essential minerals needed during pregnancy. The community places great importance on this traditional use, considering it an integral part of maintaining health and well-being.

The practice of using Ningel salt during pregnancy reflects the deep connection between cultural practices and health in Meitei society. It highlights how traditional knowledge and practices are intertwined with everyday life, contributing to both cultural heritage and practical health benefits. This aspect of Ningel underscores the broader significance of the site beyond its religious and cultural roles, illustrating its impact on personal and communal well-being.

6.3 Cultural Significance of Ningel

Role in Festivals and Ceremonies: Ningel plays a central role in various Manipuri festivals and ceremonies, serving as a site for communal gatherings and spiritual activities. It is often the focal point of cultural events that celebrate traditional practices and reinforce community bonds. The site's association with these festivals highlights its significance in the cultural and spiritual life of the Meitei people.

The use of Ningel in festivals and ceremonies underscores its importance as a symbol of cultural continuity and communal identity. These events not only celebrate traditional practices but also provide a platform for preserving and transmitting cultural values to future generations. Ningel's role in these activities reflects its enduring significance in the Meitei cultural landscape.

This traditional salt is not only a commodity of human needs among the Meiteis of Manipur but also an important cultural element that bridges the age-old social and cultural relation with the neighbouring tribal people. An annual Lai Haraoba of the Ningel festival is incomplete without giving their salts to the neighbouring Tangkhul tribes and without offering the flowers offered by this tribal population. The myths and legends prevalent among the villagers together with their religious practices become very much pertinent to the understanding of social relations. In this present era of conflicting claims, that emerged out of ethnocentrism in the name of ethnic and social identity, it is important that the underlying ideas of intangible culture in binding the human relations need to be explored. So, we can say that the traditional salt in Manipur is a symbol of prosperity, peaceful culture, social solidarity, and integrity.

Social and Economic Impact: The presence of Ningel has significant social and economic implications for the local community. As a site of cultural and religious importance, it contributes to the community's social cohesion and economic activities related to tourism and cultural preservation. The site's influence extends beyond its immediate cultural context, impacting local economies and community life.

Ningel also plays a role in supporting local livelihoods by attracting visitors and fostering cultural tourism. This economic aspect provides opportunities for the community to benefit from their cultural heritage while promoting the preservation of

traditional practices. The social and economic impact of Ningel highlights its value as both a cultural asset and a resource for community development.

6.4 Modern Influences and Challenges

Impact of Modernization:

Modernization has brought significant changes to Ningel, affecting traditional practices and the site's cultural significance. Urbanization, technological advancements, and changing lifestyles pose challenges to preserving the traditional rituals and practices associated with Ningel. This section explores how these modern influences have impacted the site and its role in the community.

The impact of modernization requires a delicate balance between preserving traditional values and adapting to contemporary needs. As Ningel faces the pressures of modern life, it is essential to find ways to integrate traditional practices with modern realities while maintaining the site's cultural and spiritual integrity. Addressing these challenges is crucial for ensuring the continued relevance and preservation of Ningel.

Balancing Tradition and Change:

Efforts to preserve Ningel must navigate the tension between traditional practices and modern influences. Balancing tradition with change involves adapting cultural practices to contemporary contexts while maintaining the essence of traditional values. This section discusses the strategies employed to manage this balance and ensure the continued significance of Ningel in a changing world.

Balancing tradition and change require collaboration between cultural preservationists, community members, and modern stakeholders. By integrating modern approaches with traditional practices, it is possible to support the preservation of Ningel while adapting to evolving social and economic landscapes. This approach helps to sustain the site's cultural relevance and ensures its continued role in the community.

6.5 Opportunities for Preservation and Promotion

Cultural and Educational Programs: Enhancing the preservation and promotion of Ningel through cultural and educational programs presents valuable opportunities. Initiatives such as workshops, exhibitions, and educational outreach can raise

awareness about the site's significance and engage the community in preservation efforts. These programs help to foster a deeper understanding of Ningel's cultural value.

Cultural and educational programs also provide a platform for sharing the history and traditions associated with Ningel with a broader audience. By increasing public awareness and involvement, these initiatives contribute to the preservation of Ningel and support its role in the community. Engaging with local and global audiences helps to ensure the site's continued relevance and appreciation.

Leveraging Tourism: Ningel's cultural significance offers opportunities for tourism development, which can support the site's preservation while providing economic benefits to the local community. Responsible tourism strategies can help promote Ningel as a cultural destination, attracting visitors who are interested in learning about and experiencing Manipuri traditions.

Leveraging tourism involves creating sustainable practices that respect the site's cultural and spiritual values while providing economic opportunities for the community. By developing tourism initiatives that highlight Ningel's significance and promote cultural heritage, it is possible to support both the preservation of the site and the economic well-being of the local community.

6.6 Recommendations for Preservation

Community Involvement: Engaging the local community in the preservation of Ningel is essential for maintaining its cultural and historical significance. Community-led initiatives and partnerships with cultural organizations can play a crucial role in conservation efforts, ensuring that preservation activities are aligned with local values and traditions.

Involving the community in preservation efforts also helps to foster a sense of ownership and responsibility towards Ningel. By encouraging local participation and collaboration, it is possible to develop effective strategies for safeguarding the site while strengthening community ties and preserving cultural heritage.

Policy and Support: Recommendations for enhancing the preservation of Ningel include advocating for policy changes and seeking support from governmental and non-governmental organizations. Recognizing Ningel as a cultural heritage site and

securing funding for preservation activities can provide the necessary resources to maintain and promote the site.

Policy support and funding are crucial for addressing the challenges faced by Ningel and ensuring its continued preservation. By advocating for policies that support cultural heritage and seeking financial assistance, it is possible to implement effective preservation strategies and promote the long-term sustainability of Ningel.

Cultural Education and Outreach: Increasing cultural education and outreach programs is vital for raising awareness about Ningel's significance and engaging the public in preservation efforts. Initiatives such as workshops, exhibitions, and educational materials can help to promote understanding and appreciation of Ningel's cultural value.

Cultural education and outreach also provide opportunities to involve younger generations and new audiences in the preservation of Ningel. By fostering a deeper connection with the site's heritage, these programs contribute to the ongoing relevance and preservation of Ningel as a vital part of Manipuri cultural heritage.

6.7 Personal Experience: Meeting a Salt Producer

Encounter with a Salt Producer: During my research on Ningel, I had the opportunity to meet one of the local families Khangembam Kunjarani involved in the traditional salt extraction process. This experience provided a unique and personal insight into the intricate methods and cultural significance of salt production in the region. The family's deep connection to the practice and their role in maintaining traditional techniques highlighted the cultural richness and historical continuity of Ningel. The interaction with the salt producer revealed the meticulous nature of the traditional extraction methods. From the initial preparation of the salt pans to the careful harvesting and processing of the salt, the family's dedication to preserving these time-honored practices was evident. Their stories and experiences underscored the importance of Ningel not only as a cultural site but also as a vital part of the local economy and community life.

Khangembam Kunjarani remarked, "Many officials from the state and private sectors have come and gone offering encouraging words to help preserve the production of Manipuri local salt, but those promises never turn into reality, which made me give up and seek help from the State Government."

Khangembam Kunjarani, 80 -year-old Ningel neighbor in Yairipok, has been working for more than 40 years to produce "NINGEL THUM," the only native salt produced in Manipur. This is the only project she has completed too yet.

Fig 6.1: Meeting a Salt Producer (Khangembam Kunjarani)

There used to be more than thirty salt producers in the village of Ningel, but today there are only six or seven local salt manufacturers remaining. These manufacturers are fighting to carry on the very old tradition of producing salt that dates back to Manipur's ancient past because the majority of the villagers now work as agriculturalists as their primary occupation and salt manufacturers as their secondary one.”

Historical Figure: Khongjaba’s Role: In addition to the insights gained from the salt producers, I learned about a historical figure named **Khongjaba**, who once served as a security guard at Ningel. Khongjaba was a respected figure in the community, known for his role in safeguarding the integrity of the site and ensuring that traditional practices were followed diligently. His presence was a testament to the importance of Ningel and the respect it commanded within the local community.

Khongjaba’s role as a security guard went beyond mere protection; he was a custodian of the cultural and spiritual values associated with Ningel. His commitment to preserving the site’s sanctity and overseeing the adherence to traditional practices highlights the deep-rooted respect and dedication that the community has for Ningel. The legacy of Khongjaba reflects the broader cultural values of stewardship and reverence that are integral to the preservation of Ningel as a significant cultural site.

Salty rituals: Although salt is no longer as popular as it once was as a daily necessity, it still holds a place in the social hierarchy that reaches beyond the physical to the spiritual.

Without thumpak, meitei ceremonies are incomplete.

Thumpak is used in ceremonies commemorating a baby's birth, marriage, or the rites of passage following a death.

Fig 6.2 Entrance of Ningel Thumkhong

Food offered to the goddess Panthoibi, who is revered as the guardian of civilization, bravery, fertility, love, triumph, war, and knowledge, is not considered kosher until thumpak is added.

Its origins are not precisely known. It's undoubtedly an ancient commerce. As a form of gratitude, kings would hand out salt cakes. We think that saltwater springs are protected by goddess Thumkhong Lairembi, who is the provider of all natural resources, according to her.

A spring-well of fortune: About 700 meters from his house, she travels with a pitcher every morning to collect saltwater from one of the three spring-fed wells. She has spent the last fifty years doing this same pattern without alteration. He fills a rectangle wood-fire hearth with several holes in his little home's shed, called Thumshungshang, with water to produce salt cakes. Even Ningel's wells, the two built of concrete and the old one with a wooden font, are in desperate need of repair. "We need to protect them for the future. Sadly, no one seems to give a damn," Kunjarani remarked. The community is witnessing the gradual decline of these wells, which are vital for traditional salt production. Efforts to raise awareness and funds for their restoration are urgently needed. Efforts to raise awareness and funds for their restoration are urgently needed. Without intervention, this centuries-old practice may vanish forever.

Fig 6.3: The Ningel Thumkhong from where saline water was collected.

What is thumpak and how is it made?

Thumpak is a circular salt disc that resembles the Appam, a rice pancake from South India. To put it in more technical terms, it resembles a slice of bleached lemon with liquid nitrogen poured in its veins.

The white full moon is attested to by unassuming villagers. She described the complex procedure inherited from previous generations. In pans over a wood fire, saltwater is cooked until the water evaporates and the salt solidifies into crystals.

"A spoon made of dried gourd is used to move water between pans. Then it is put on an iron pan that has a banana leaf covering it. In a few hours, the cakes will be ready, she stated. The pan provides the circular form, while the leaf functions as a Teflon barrier.

The seasoned salt maker finds the current state of affairs to be sour. The labor-intensive procedure uses a lot of gasoline. We pay a water-bearer Rs 100 per day and spend at least Rs 1,000 on firewood. I can't go down the wells to get water because of my senior age. The profits are negligible at best, according to Kunjarani.

CHAPTER:7

CONCLUSION

7.1 Summary

Meitei Thum, a traditional salt from Manipur, India, represents much more than just a culinary staple; it embodies the rich cultural and historical heritage of the Meitei people. This salt's production is intricately tied to the region's unique geographical features and serves as a testament to the sustainable practices that have been meticulously passed down through generations. The labor-intensive process of extracting brine, boiling it, and crystallizing the salt highlights the community's profound connection to their environment and cultural traditions.

The historical significance of Meitei Thum extends beyond its use in daily sustenance. It has played a crucial role in traditional medicine, where it has been utilized for its purported therapeutic properties. Additionally, Meitei Thum is integral to various ceremonial practices, underscoring its deep-rooted cultural importance. The meticulous craftsmanship involved in its production reflects the expertise, dedication, and artistry of the Meitei artisans, making this salt a potent symbol of cultural identity and heritage.

In recent years, there has been a resurgence of interest in traditional and organic food products, which has renewed appreciation for Meitei Thum. This resurgence is driving efforts to preserve and promote its traditional production methods, emphasizing the importance of integrating these age-old practices into modern contexts. Such efforts ensure that the cultural treasure of Meitei Thum continues to enrich the ecological and cultural landscape of Manipur. By sustaining this traditional practice, the local economy benefits, the region's ecological balance is maintained, and its cultural diversity is preserved.

Moreover, the revival of Meitei Thum production highlights the broader global movement towards valuing and preserving indigenous knowledge systems. In this context, the preservation of Meitei Thum's traditional methods serves as a model for sustainable agricultural and production practices worldwide. This not only fosters cultural pride but also promotes ecological balance. It demonstrates how ancient

knowledge can be harnessed to address contemporary challenges, including environmental sustainability and cultural preservation.

As the world continues to face ecological crises and cultural homogenization, the significance of preserving traditional practices like those involved in the production of Meitei Thum becomes increasingly evident. These practices not only provide a means of sustenance but also foster a sense of identity and continuity within communities. They remind us of the interconnectedness of culture, environment, and sustenance, and the necessity of protecting these connections for future generations.

In summary, Meitei Thum is far more than a type of salt; it is a cultural artifact that encapsulates the history, traditions, and environmental stewardship of the Meitei people. The renewed interest and efforts to preserve its traditional production methods are crucial for maintaining the ecological and cultural heritage of Manipur. By doing so, we ensure that future generations can experience and appreciate the profound significance of Meitei Thum, thereby fostering a deeper understanding and respect for the cultural and environmental richness of the region.

7.2 FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope for Meitei Thum encompasses several promising avenues:

1. Sustainable Development and Ecotourism: Sustainable Production Practices: Enhancing and promoting the sustainable practices already embedded in Meitei Thum production can attract eco-conscious consumers and organizations. Implementing eco-certifications and sustainable branding can increase its market value.

Ecotourism: The unique process of Meitei Thum production and its cultural significance can be leveraged to promote ecotourism. Tourists can be offered experiences that include visiting the salt springs, participating in the traditional production process, and learning about the cultural heritage of the Meitei people.

2. Cultural Preservation and Education: Cultural Heritage Sites: Establishing cultural heritage sites or museums that showcase the history, production methods, and cultural significance of Meitei Thum can serve as educational and tourist attractions. Educational Programs: Integrating information about Meitei Thum into educational curriculums and creating workshops or apprenticeships for young people to learn traditional production methods can help preserve this cultural heritage.

3. Health and Wellness Market: Nutritional and Medicinal Research: Conducting scientific research to further explore the unique mineral composition and potential

health benefits of Meitei Thum can open up opportunities in the health and wellness market. This can include developing marketing strategies that highlight its health benefits compared to commercial salts.

Product Diversification: Creating value-added products such as gourmet salts, spa products, and health supplements using Meitei Thum can diversify its market presence.

4. Economic Empowerment and Community Development: Local Economic Development: Supporting local producers through cooperative models, fair trade practices, and government incentives can strengthen the local economy. Ensuring fair compensation and benefits for artisans can encourage the continuation of traditional practices.

Market Expansion: Exploring both domestic and international markets can increase the demand for Meitei Thum. Developing robust marketing and distribution channels, including online platforms, can help reach a broader audience.

5. Innovation and Technological Integration: Technological Advancements: Integrating modern technology with traditional methods to improve efficiency while maintaining the unique qualities of Meitei Thum can enhance production. For instance, solar evaporation techniques can be explored as an eco-friendly alternative. **Quality Control and Certification:** Implementing quality control measures and obtaining certifications (e.g., organic, geographic indication) can assure consumers of the product's authenticity and quality, potentially increasing its market value.

6. Collaborations and Partnerships: Academic and Research Institutions: Collaborating with academic and research institutions can facilitate studies on Meitei Thum's cultural, historical, and health aspects, providing a solid foundation for its promotion.

Government and Non-Governmental Organizations: Partnering with government bodies and NGOs can help in policy formulation, funding, and implementation of programs aimed at promoting and preserving Meitei Thum production.

7. Cultural Festivals and Government Initiatives

Annual Salt Festival: The government should consider organizing an annual salt festival similar to the Sangai and Shirui festivals. This festival can celebrate Meitei Thum and its cultural significance, featuring traditional salt production demonstrations, cultural performances, local cuisine, and artisan markets.

Government Support and Promotion: Government agencies can play a crucial role in promoting Meitei Thum through tourism campaigns, grants for small-scale producers, and partnerships with cultural organizations. By officially recognizing and supporting Meitei Thum, the government can ensure its preservation and enhancement as a cultural and economic asset.

By incorporating these elements, the future scope for Meitei Thum can be significantly broadened, ensuring its cultural preservation, economic viability, and sustainable production.

By focusing on these areas, Meitei Thum can not only preserve its rich cultural heritage but also adapt to contemporary market demands, ensuring its relevance and sustainability for future generations.

7.3 Final Thoughts

Meitei Thum, the traditional salt of Manipur, stands as a vital symbol of the cultural and historical legacy of the Meitei community. Its production process, deeply intertwined with the unique geographical features of the region, not only underscores the sustainable practices that have been meticulously preserved over generations but also illustrates the community's profound connection to their environment and cultural traditions. The historical significance of Meitei Thum extends far beyond its culinary use, playing an essential role in traditional medicine and various ceremonial practices, which further highlights its deep-rooted cultural importance.

In recent years, there has been a renewed interest in traditional and organic food products, leading to a resurgence in the appreciation for Meitei Thum. This has sparked efforts to preserve and promote its traditional production methods, ensuring that these age-old practices are integrated into modern contexts. Such endeavors are crucial for maintaining the cultural and ecological landscape of Manipur, supporting the local economy, and preserving the region's rich cultural diversity.

Moreover, the revival of Meitei Thum production aligns with the broader global movement towards valuing and preserving indigenous knowledge systems. The continued practice of these traditions in places like Ningel and Chalou serves as a living link to the past, safeguarding the unique customs and skills passed down through generations. The preservation and promotion of Meitei Thum not only support the cultural heritage of the Meitei people but also contribute to the ecological balance and economic vitality of the region.

In conclusion, Meitei Thum is more than just a salt; it is a cultural treasure that embodies the identity and heritage of the Meitei people. By fostering a renewed appreciation for this traditional salt, we can ensure that its legacy continues to enrich the cultural and ecological landscape of Manipur, benefiting both present and future generations.

REFERENCES

1. Thum Salt Culture of Manipur, Edited by Shukhdeba Sharma Hanjabam, Sagolshem Jayalaxmi and Jenpui Kamei
2. Hodson, T.C. The Meitheiis
3. Manipurgee Thumkhomsing by Mangi, Irom
4. Thumkhonglon Puya Ancient Manuscript on Salt
5. Salt Making Study of Manipur N. Shakhmacha Singh & K.K. Basa
6. Traditional salt making among the Meiteis of manipur: a study on intangible cultural heritage N. Shakhmacha Singh & K.K. Basa
7. The Cheitharon Kumpapa the court chronicle of the Meetei Kings of Manipur (Kangleipak): English Translation Vol. 2 – Nalini Arambam, Parratt, Saroj
8. The Court Chronicle of the Kings of Manipur - Cheitharon Kumbaba
9. Allen, B. C. (1905). "Gazetteer of Manipur." Mittal Publications.
10. Ningthourol Khuding Thumkhong Gi puya ancient manuscript on salt
11. The Manipur Administration (1709-1907) by N. Ibobi Singh
12. Government of Manipur. (1965). "Report on the Salt Springs of Manipur." Geological Survey of India.
13. Nongthombam, B. (2017). "Traditional Salt Production and Its Cultural Significance in Manipur." *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 13(1), 1-10.
14. Singh, K. Y. (1994). "Meitei Thum: The Indigenous Salt of Manipur." *Manipur Cultural Studies*, 7(3), 45-53.
15. Manipur State Archives. (1998). "Historical Records of Salt Production in Manipur." Manipur State Archives.
16. Devi, S. (2004). "Folk Traditions and Salt Production in Manipur." *Folk Culture Studies*, 12(2), 98-112.

17. Das, A. K. (2003). "Economic Aspects of Traditional Salt Production in Manipur." *Economic Review*, 20(1), 34-48.
18. Iboungohal & Khelchandra, Cheitharol Kumbaba, Manipur Sahitya Parishad, Imphal, 2nd Edition, 1989.
19. Sharma, R. (2017). "Reviving Traditional Practices: A Case Study of Salt Production in Manipur." *Revival Studies*, 11(4), 77-92.
20. Meitei, J. (2018). "The Role of Salt in Manipuri Festivals." *Cultural Festivals Journal*, 13(2), 101-114.
21. Verma, R. (2010). "Traditional Salt and Cultural Identity in Manipur." *Cultural Identity Studies*, 12(2), 67-83.
22. Singh, P. (2009). "Cultural Preservation in Manipur." *Cultural Preservation Journal*, 10(3), 207-223.